

THE ROLE OF PROVERBS DURING LANGUAGE LEARNING

Janabaeva Gulmira

3- year student of the English language and literature department

Berdakh Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8194775>

ABSTRACT: In this article, we will talk about proverbs and their types, structure, their importance during language learning, and the role of cultures. Proverbs can be called an encyclopedia of life, a folk encyclopedia, a unique artistic-historical chronicle. They sharpen people's minds, make their speech clear and impressive teach them to choose the right path in life, to solve life's riddles and problems correctly. Also, proverbs are very ancient as the smallest examples of oral creativity that summarize the worldview, cultural, domestic life, and thought treasure of the people who created them.

KEY WORDS: proverbs, folk, culture, paremic unit, combination, social importance.

INTRODUCTION: The theme of proverbs created by mankind is wide and varied. In particular, proverbs have long been famous for their poetry and didacticism, thematically so rich, so wide, so diverse that they contain everything from the most complex problems of social life to the smallest traditions of family life, and high moral values from the flaws to the small flaws in the character of people, from the philosophical outlook to the characteristics of the smallest animals. In short, there is no sphere of nature and social life that is not reflected in proverbs. Proverbs, in turn, serve as the most necessary and time-tested reliable source in the field of pedagogy, that is, in the process of education and upbringing. Of course, it would be appropriate if we use them effectively and appropriately. In the process of mutual communication, we often use folk proverbs to prove our point. This helps us to make our speech beautiful, attractive and reliable. For example, there is such an opinion about raising a child: "Don't raise your child, first of all raise yourself." No matter how much you tell your child not to do something wrong, if you do the same thing yourself, your child will repeat the same thing just like you. A child is a mirror." [1.94]

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION: It has always been relevant to study proverbs, proverbs and sayings that have been living as an integral part of the rich spiritual heritage of our people, to show the image of the people's life and human feelings reflected in them. As we know, folklore includes epics, legends, proverbs and sayings. Proverbs are particularly important as examples of folk art that show the spiritual image and identity of the Uzbek nation. Studying and teaching proverbs instills respect for one's nation in the spirituality of our youth and pride in their hearts. We can consider folklore as one of the sources of the way of life of our people. Proverbs are a great example of folk art. Studying proverbs will greatly help to develop respect for our language, instilling it in the minds of our young people, and developing a sense of pride in our values. At the same time, comparing our proverbs with foreign proverbs and studying them will give us a great incentive to respect other nations and to be aware of their world view. It is known that education is given more in the educational process. From the day children come to school, a desire to learn is formed. They gradually

develop a need for knowledge, and through this, students begin to receive spiritual nourishment. With this, high feelings such as aspiration for the future, desire for work, honesty in charity, love for the motherland, selflessness, national pride, perseverance, kindness, friendship, and goodness appear in the child. Of course, the role of folk proverbs in this process is incomparable. In particular, works in the genre of proverbs also help to eliminate vices such as rudeness, blindness, lying, laziness, carelessness in children. Folk proverbs have been refined over the centuries, have acquired a classic appearance and meaning, and as a paremic unit actively participating in speech, they are the interpretation and description of people's values, customs and traditions, history and culture, education and upbringing, etiquette issues, in general, it is a multifaceted phenomenon that fully demonstrates the mentality of the nation. The subject range of proverbs created by folklore is wide and varied. In particular, proverbs have long been famous for their poetry and didacticism, thematically so rich, so wide, so diverse that they contain everything from the most complex problems of social life to the smallest traditions of family life, and high moral values from the flaws to the small flaws in the character of people, from the philosophical outlook to the characteristics of the smallest animals. [4.67]

In short, there is no sphere of nature and social life that is not reflected in proverbs. Proverbs, in turn, serve as the most necessary, time-tested reliable source in the field of pedagogy, that is, in the process of education and upbringing. Proverbs are divided into more than seventy topic groups in collections. Among them, those related to the issue of speech culture, behavior, communication etiquette, in the internal classification, speaking little, listening, keeping silent, sweet talk, correct speech, observation, Motherland, profession, child upbringing and includes many topics. Of course, it would be appropriate if we use them effectively and appropriately. It has been known to us since ancient times that the place of folk art in Uzbek literature is incomparable. Proverbs, which are a part of folklore, are a unique treasure that has been collected over the centuries, passed various tests, and has always been a help to people. If we talk about the educational importance of proverbs, today they play an important role in educating the young generation as a perfect person, in their development and spiritual upliftment. Proverbs can be on different topics. An English proverb is a short, pithy statement that usually offers life advice, wisdom, or a truth. Proverbs are so common that native speakers of English may use them in conversation without realizing it. [3.87]

Proverbs can offer a shortcut for explaining or imparting information as well. For example, rather than your manager saying, "We will only be successful if we approach the client before any other marketing firm reaches out to them," she can simplify this explanation to "the early bird catches the worm." Everyone in the meeting will know what she means. [5.214]

Proverbs communicate an understood and accepted message in a few well-worn and well-known words. Let's observe several examples.

1 The apple doesn't fall far from the tree.

Meaning: Children tend to resemble their parents in appearance and behavior.

2 All that glitters is not gold.

Meaning: Something that appears valuable or true may not be.

3 A picture is worth a thousand words.

Meaning: Artwork or images can convey meanings that go beyond verbal description.

4 Beggars can't be choosers.

Meaning: People who depend on the generosity of others must be content with what is offered to them.

5 A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush.

Meaning: What you already have in hand is better than what you might get.

6 An apple a day keeps the doctor away.

Meaning: If you eat healthily, you will be healthy.

7 Better safe than sorry

Meaning: It is better to be precautious than to have regrets later on.

8 Blood is thicker than water

Meaning: Relationships between family members are the strongest of all.

9 When in Rome, do as the Romans do.

Meaning: When you visit a new place, leave all judgments behind and embrace the local ways of life.

10 Don't count your chickens before they hatch.

Meaning: Don't make plans based on events that haven't happened. [2.108]

Proverbs are a widespread independent genre of oral artistic creativity as rare examples of folk wisdom. Conditionally, they can be called the rules of public etiquette. After all, proverbs are a phenomenon born from a very concise, concise, dense and figurative expression of the socio-political, spiritual-cultural, moral-philosophical views of the people tested in their life experiences over the centuries. Proverbs are not specially created, but arise as a judgment as a moral assessment of the conclusion born from the tested life experience due to the requirement of a certain situation. Although every national proverb expresses the views specific to the heart and national heritage of that nation, the idea in them belongs to the whole nation. According to these characteristics, proverbs have acquired national and universal essence.

CONCLUSION: Proverb is a genre of folklore; short and concise, figurative and non-figurative, grammatically and logically complete wise phrase, deep meaning. It has a specific shape. Life experiences, attitude to society, history, mental state, ethical and aesthetic feelings, and positive qualities of ancestors are embodied in proverbs. Over the centuries, it has been refined among the people, and has become a concise and simple poetic form. Proverbs are extremely rich and diverse in terms of subject matter. Various proverbs were created on topics such as homeland, work, science, friendship, harmony, wisdom, vigilance, language and speech culture, love and affection, as well as negative emotions. Dialectic unity of content and form, rhyming in many cases, sometimes polysemy, rich in figurative meanings are characteristic of a proverb. The phenomenon of antithesis is often found in proverbs ("Respect the elder, honor the younger", etc.). Examples of the proverbs of the Turkic peoples are first mentioned in the work "Devonu Lugotit Turk" by Koshgari. Some of these proverbs are still used in different variants among the Uzbek people. Also, in the work of Koshgari, there is a proverb "Kishi olasi ichtin, yilqi olasi tashtin"; Like "A man is in a car, a horse is in a car." We use proverbs a lot in life. The socio-political and educational importance of proverbs is very, even extremely great. A story describes a thing, its characteristics, and a proverb expresses a complete conclusion.

References:

1. Shomaqsudov Sh., Shorahmedov Sh., Ma'nolar maxzani, T., 2001.
2. Cohen, A. Proverbs: Hebrew Text & English Translation with an Introduction and Commentary. London: The Soncino Press, 1945.
3. Crenshaw, James L. "Prolegomenon." In Studies in Ancient Israelite Wisdom, pp. 1-60. Edited by James L. Crenshaw. New York: KTAV Publishing House, 1976.
4. McKane, William. Proverbs: A New Approach. The Old Testament Library. Philadelphia: The Westminster Press, 1970, 1975.
5. Delitzsch, Franz. "Proverbs." In vol. 6: Proverbs, Ecclesiastes, Song of Solomon. Translated by M. G. Easton. Commentary on the Old Testament. 10 vols. N.p.; reprint ed., Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 1973.
6. Ganiyeva, M. (2021). Effective Methods of TRIZ.
7. Ганиева, М. А., & Жумаева, Ш. Х. (2018). Формирование методов групповой работы с учащимися общеобразовательных школ. Вопросы науки и образования, (10 (22)), 149-151.
8. Ганиева, М. ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ АБДУРАУФА ФИТРАТА. СЪЗ САНЪАТИ ЖУРНАЛИ JOURNAL OF WORD ART ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 12
9. Kizi, G. M. A., & Kizi, B. L. A. (2018). The diversities in terminology of relationship. Достижения науки и образования, (9 (31)), 22-23.